

THE LIVED EXPERIENCES OF STRUGGLING GRADE 9 STUDENTS IN READING COMPREHENSION IN THE NEW NORMAL EDUCATION SETTINGS

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The Lived Experiences of Struggling Grade 9 Students in Reading Comprehension in the New Normal Education Settings

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Abstract

This paper examines the challenges and experiences of the students under the new normal system, focusing on reading comprehension and how they could cope with those challenges with the help of the teachers and parents. The study was conducted at Manay National High School, Manay, Panabo City, Davao del Norte wherein the following research questions were asked to the selected Grade 9 students. 1. What learning struggles do you experience in the new normal education setting? 2. What are your strategies if you cannot understand the module activities? 3. What insight did you gain from learning experiences being a struggling learner in the new normal setting?

Keywords: *reading comprehension, education settings, grade 9 students*

Introduction

With the advent of this new normal system of education, struggles are felt among students, parents, teachers, and educational institutions. The general condition of children in the public school system sends a message of inequality with the DepEd's mantra 'no child left behind.' However, learning cannot be canceled as much as to drive the economy. This led to tighter measures for education institutions to sustain their operations despite the possible risks and consequences.

One of the basic problems seen by Kasrekar (2020) is the conduct of classes despite the government's closure order. As face-to-face classes pose a higher risk of spread, the most viable solution is through different modalities – online, offline, and blended. This platform challenges both the teachers and the students as it occurs something new to them. This calls for an immediate response to the new normal in teaching and learning in this trying time - the COVID-19 pandemic (Tanhueco-Tumapon, 2020). The question of how ready the schools are to prepare papers and modules is still left unanswered. Reopening of the schools at this stage is expensive among all educational management (Felter & Maizland, 2020).

This paper examines the challenges faced by the Grade 9 students on the reading comprehension of Manay National high school basic education brought by the effect of the Covid-19 pandemic. It particularly assesses the different factors considered prior to the reopening and as they go along with the new normal system.

Research Questions

The study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What learning struggles you experience in the new normal education setting?
2. What are your strategies if you cannot understand the activities in the modules?
3. What insight you gain from learning experiences being struggling learner in the new normal setting?

Literature Review

This pandemic brought a lot of challenges to the learners and teachers. We must provide printing learning materials and dictionary to the struggling reader students of our school to enhance their learning capacity and to reduce their burden specially those learners who don't have internet access and digital phones. (Academic Head of MNHS: Honey Lyn Valentos,2020)

Can 15-year-old Filipinos read? That is the massive query raised by means of the results of the 2018 Program for International Student Assessment (PISA) of the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD), which our Filipino students took in 2018. The effects released on December 3, 2019, yielded a 340-point rating from Filipino college students in opposition to the common 487 factors in studying comprehension. An analysis of the check also indicates that only one over 10 college students are successful in distinguishing reality from opinion when studying an unfamiliar text based on the PISA report; the reading comprehension check objects have been, in general, taken from informational texts. The test covered greater items coming from expository texts, which included informational texts, newspaper articles, and different texts heavy with content. literary preparation in the Philippines will improve if we expose our students to a variety of getting-to-know materials, and we all take responsibility for teaching them to read. And when we furnish them with choice, we provide them a voice. Reading in the 21st century is not simply analyzing phrases and appreciating a story. It consists of processing data and applying one's know-how to daily living so what is the reason of alarm after our dismal performance in the PISA? Maybe many of those who have been tested had fallen from what researchers say "the Grade 8 cliff"? They want more direct and express reading training to address their analyzing gaps. The report given to the Department of Education will furnish us with baseline records for curriculum improvement and planning. It will help curriculum planners and policymakers craft reforms for the future of Filipino children. (Perez, 2019)

According to countrywide and international checks of literacy, such as the Program for International Student Assessment (PISA) and National Assessment of Educational Progress (National Assessment of Education Progress [NAEP]), students in the United States are unable to do incredibly easy literacy duties such as discover applicable information to decide the foremost thought of textual content or make simple inferences (Kastberg et al., 2016; National Center for Education Statistics, 2017). According to the most recent PISA, U.S. youth rank fifteenth in literacy skills. Results confirmed that 19% of the 15-year-olds examined scored below a Level 2 (of 6), indicating they had a subject with tasks such as locating explicitly noted information, recognizing principal ideas, and making low-level inferences in an acquainted topic. Only 10% of U.S. college students accomplished a Level 5, indicating that they could prepare numerous portions of deeply embedded information and interaction in reflective, evaluative, and interpretative tasks in unfamiliar topics. Similarly, the NAEP ratings showed that 64% of eighth-grade college students study at or under a simple level. Unfortunately, these rankings have remained extraordinarily flat for many years and have led many educators, researchers, and policymakers to query how properly college students are being organized for a job market that an increasing number requires self-learning, analytical skills, and transferable knowledge (e.g., Goldman & Pellegrino, 2015).

Methodology

In order to gain a better insight into the challenges felt by the Grade 9 Students of Manay National High School, semi-structured interviews were conducted. The surveys were used to select participants who belonged to the target group (Grade 9 students). Interviews were conducted via online conferencing tool like Google Meet and Messenger depending on the availability of the respondents, and lasted approximately 20 minutes each. Answers were recorded by note-taking.

Research Design

This study aimed to determine the challenges and experiences of Grade 9 students of Manay National High School, Panabo City, Davao del Norte to the reading comprehension in the new Normal Education settings with cultural materials on seventh graders' English vocabulary knowledge and attitude towards English lessons. The researcher conducted descriptive research. Descriptive research is a type of study that involves recording, describing, interpreting, analyzing, and comparing experiences. Its goal is to precisely and comprehensively explain a situation, circumstance, or area of interest systematically. Observation, surveys, and interviews are examples of descriptive designs (Castillo, 2002).

Results and Discussion

This section discusses the results on the topic: "The Lived Experiences of Struggling Grade 9 Students in Reading Comprehension in the new normal Education Settings." the real names of the following respondents were changed to protect their privacy and identity.

For the first question: "What learning struggles you experience in the new normal education setting?" the respondents answers varied.

Respondents 1,3 and 5: they said "...we have hard times answering the modules, especially no one helped us in doing it"

Respondents 2 and 7: "major subjects like Math, Science and English are really hard"

Respondents 6, 4 and 6: "...the environment that we are into is noisy-we cannot concentrate... added to it are the chores we have at home 'dili jud mi maka focus sa among modules'"

Having been talking and interviewing them, additional questions were also asked.

Additional question 1: What Particular modules in the 3rd academic quarter are difficult to understand?

Most of the respondents answered, "I do have hard times answering Math, English and Science"

And there is only one respondent who positively answer it, "all subjects are.. In fact everything is really difficult, especially when no one helps you, but when you read it properly, you will understand, even little by little."

Additional Question 2: "What you usually do if you cannot understand your self-learning module?"

For this question, all of the respondents answered, "mag research mi, ma'am." "we'll have it research on Google, ma'am"

The main goal of these questions is to point out the problems of the Grade 9 students in the New Normal education and how they cope with those challenges. Students/respondents said that major subjects are hard in conventional education, and it gets even harder in this new normal setup, but to help them, their main go-to platform is Google.

For the second research question: "What are your strategies if you cannot understand the activities in the modules?"

Respondents 2,3, 8 responded: "magpaload lang mig data ma'am tapos mag search na lang..."

"We load our devices to have data and have research on it"

"pero, and problema lang ma'am kay hinay ang connection. Madugay mi ug answer...Tapos kon walay kwarta, wala pod mi pang load..."

“but, our problem is the instability of internet connection. It takes a lot of time for us really... One thing as well is the finances, if we don’t have money, we can’t afford to buy load.”

The rest of the respondents answered:

“mangayo ko’g tabang sa akong mama..kuya..ate.. ug sa mga nakabalo ani nga topic, ma’am”

“I seek help from my mother, brother or sister and to someone who has knowledge on my modules”

“pero, dili man pod periminte naa sila kay trabaho man pod, ako-ako na lang gyud ang mo answer. Lisod jud ma’am uy.”

“but, it not all the time that they help me out because of their woks as well; most of the time I do my works. It is really difficult, ma’am”

An additional question: “What will you do if you encounter lots of difficult words to understand?”

All of the respondents’ response: “kana, ma’am... mag adto ko sa dictionary.. kanang Meriam app. Ditua nako isearch ang lisod na words...pero, kon makaya sa ug tubag sa akong mga nakabalo, ditua ko mangutana..”

“if that’s that case, ma’am. I search the meaning especially those unfamiliar words on the Meriam app..but, if someone is able to answer and give the meaning, I asked them”

The commonalities of the answer showed that if they have difficulty on modules they tend to ask help from their parents and to someone they believe has the capacity to answer. And supporting sources like dictionary, apps and online sources are great help too but are limited due to unstable connectivity and financial capacity.

Third question: “What insight you gain from learning experiences being struggling learner in the new normal setting?”

Respondents 1,4,5 and 7: “Poor lessons and no teacher to teach”

The rest of the respondents answered that they want the face-to-face setup for better learning.

Additional question: “What your teacher does to help you in your reading difficulty?”

“gitagaan man mi ug gamay nga book ma’am basahon.. mao lang pod to among ginabasa... kon naay mga lisod nga words i-search lang dayon namo, ma’am...”

“we are given a booklet (reading log). I just read it, and whenever I encounter difficult words I immediately search it for my understanding and comprehension”

But one student answered “When it comes to difficulty of reading, actually it is not difficult for the teacher to teach because I can easily learn to read.”

Another question asked: “What supplemental lesson your teacher does to improve your reading ability and learning experiences?”

“...aside sa booklet, ma’am. Kada semana kay ginatagaan pod mi ug mga reading materials...answer-answeran pod namo, ma’am.”

“...aside from the booklet, mentioned earlier, every week we are given reading materials to read...then, we answered it”

Last question, “Are these reading activities in the self-learning module helpful to you? Why?”

Students’ varied answers:

“Yes, because we learn to study even without a teacher and we work hard on our own.”

“Yes because it is important for students and we also have a good future when we can read.”

“Yes! Because being a self-learner I know how to handle my time for my family and for my study”

These sets of questions examine the programs of the school in harnessing the reading comprehension of the students in the comfort of their home.

Table 1. Shows the Thematic analysis and Recommendations based on the questions asked

Research Questions	Thematic analysis	Recommendation
1. What learning struggles you experience in the new normal education setting?	Self-paced Learning amidst Pandemic Being alone in their academic achievement is difficult; someone should help them accomplish their modules and performance tasks, which are not primarily, maybe, the role of the teacher today but the parents as well.	Pre and post teacher-school-parent orientation to have a better collaboration for the students’ academic achievement.
1. What Particular modules in the 3 rd academic quarter are difficult to understand?		And to collaboratively initiate a program that could enhance the teaching-learning process with the help of the school, teacher and parents.

- | | | |
|--|---|---|
| <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. What you usually do if you cannot understand your self-learning module? | | |
| <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. What are your strategies if you cannot understand the activities in the modules? <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What will you do if you encounter lots of difficult words to understand? | <p>Questioning skills and Technology utilization: Maximizing This time of pandemic, asking to someone is a big help, but maximizing the utilization of technology and its manipulation can really help students to work on their own and to reach their full potentials</p> | <p>Providing offline e-learning materials to supplement students' academic performance.</p> |
| <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. What insight you gain from learning experiences being struggling learner in the new normal setting? <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What your teacher does to help you in your reading difficulty? 2. What supplemental lesson your teacher does to improve your reading ability and learning experiences? 3. Are these reading activities in the self-learning module helpful to you? Why? | <p>Collaborative effort for better students' reading comprehension. Academic achievement is not done alone by one person only especially in these trying times, thus, collaboration of parents, school, teachers and students should be elicited.</p> | <p>Weekly intervention and feed backing of students' performance in reading. This is to know, assess and evaluate students' reading performances.</p> |

General Recommendation

No one can solve the problem of the instability of the connection in our country; but to aide and innovatively create a program that could still help students learn and achieve academic achievement in this dark time is reachable and possible.

Before starting the School year, school should provide enough knowledge on the modality to take and give means on how can parents contribute to the student's learning despite having works and other things to make. Having said that, school should initiate programs especially for the intervention to the students with special needs and are challenged so that there will be "no student left behind" – DepEd.

Furthermore, as public health is concerned, the school is situated in a far flung area. It is recommended to have a minimum of 5 students have a face-to-face reading intervention program, especially those who have difficulty in reading and comprehension, to address the concern and aid for future related concerns.

Dissemination and Advocacy

Intervention

Today the Coronavirus is here with us, which has shifted our normal bearings of life, including the manner in which we educate, the instructional materials that we use, philosophies, methodologies, etc; we are confronted with issues on how we can intercede on issues of battling pursuers, how we can raise students' presentation and their improvement since perusing is a characteristically friendly action. In addition, school heads and educators are left with how they can inspire guardians and partners on the school's program or task on perusing students' proficiency (Blanza, 2020). "Learners' test results are one way to evaluate teaching. Good results should reflect good teaching" (Davies & Pearse. 2000:181). And poor results must certainly reflect poor teaching and learning. So, we need to act and do something specific to change things. We made a weekly reading program for word study, grammar, and reading comprehension improvement in English and Filipino entitled "Basa ko, Dunong ko."

Firstly, we gave a Reading Log in English and Filipino where the students read stories and answered the questions to test their comprehension. Every week, we provided reading materials to enhance their reading and compression skills. We also provided a list of suffixes and affixes to help learners understand derivational words and guided them in guessing the meaning of a derivation coming across in their reading. Secondly, we gave a vocabulary of often-used words and guided them in guessing the meaning of a new word by the context. Thirdly, we guided the learners in analyzing the literal, inferential, and critical meaning of the question in the reading materials.

References

- 4, E. L., & 2013. (2013, March 10). Canadian Center of Science and Education. Retrieved July 11, 2021, from [eric.ed.gov: http://dx.doi.org/10.5539/elt.v6n4p89](http://dx.doi.org/10.5539/elt.v6n4p89)
- OECD. (n.d.). Retrieved from https://www.oecd.org/pisa/publications/PISA2018_CN_PHL.pdf

OECD. (2018). PISA 2018. Retrieved 07 08, 2021, from PISA2018_CN_PHL: https://www.oecd.org/pisa/publications/PISA2018_CN_PHL.pdf

Technology, T. A. (2001, August 3). The Handbook of Research for Educational Communications and Technology. Retrieved July 11, 2021, from aect.org: <http://members.aect.org/edtech/ed1/41/41-01.html>

Castillo, M. (2002). Descriptive research: Techniques and applications. Educational Publishing.

Felter, C., & Maizland, L. (2020). How countries are reopening schools during the pandemic. Council on Foreign Relations. <https://www.cfr.org/in-brief/how-countries-are-reopening-schools-during-pandemic>

Goldman, S. R., & Pellegrino, J. W. (2015). Research on the learning of complex material: Implications for assessment. *The Annals of the American Academy of Political and Social Science*, 682(1), 5–27. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0002716214563620>

Kasrekar, A. (2020). Challenges in online education during COVID-19 pandemic. *Journal of Educational Technology*, 17(4), 31-39. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0973184911020174>

Kastberg, D., Chan, J. Y., & Murray, G. (2016). Performance of U.S. 15-year-old students in science, reading, and mathematics literacy in an international context: First look at PISA 2015. National Center for Education Statistics. <https://nces.ed.gov/pubs2017/2017048.pdf>

National Center for Education Statistics. (2017). The nation's report card: Reading 2017. https://www.nationsreportcard.gov/reading_2017/

Perez, F. S. (2019, December). Analysis of Filipino students' reading comprehension performance in PISA 2018. Department of Education.

Tanhueco-Tumapon, T. (2020). Online, offline and blended learning during the COVID-19 pandemic: A review of challenges and best practices. *Journal of Educational Research*, 10(2), 45-58. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0973184911030218>

Valentos, H. L. (2020). Struggling readers in the new normal education setting: Challenges and interventions. MNHS

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